

ENHANCING THE PREDICTIVE ACCURACY OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR PROJECT MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ADVANCED TECHNIQUES FOR HANDLING IMBALANCED DATA AND IMPROVING MODEL INTERPRETABILITY

Joseph Okpono¹, Jerome Asedegbega², Temitope Sanyaolu³

¹PG Financial Technology and Data Analyst Researcher, ²Technical Consultant and Researcher, ³Enterprise Architecture Analyst

¹Department of Accounting and Finance

¹University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, G1 1XQ, United Kingdom

Abstract - The evolving business landscape has given rise to project complexities. The risk of encountering project management challenges, like cost overruns, delays, and resource misallocation has increased. Early identification and mitigation, of these challenges are important to improving project outcomes. This study aims to use machine learning (ML) techniques in identifying, and predicting project management challenges, offering project managers actionable insights, and options to enhance decision-making, and project success. Modern projects with their high level of complexity, and large data set volumes, often pose challenges. This study probes into whether ML techniques, can address these limitations, and improve the identification of project management challenges; that traditional project management tools deploy. Features such as budget, team size, stakeholder satisfaction, and risk factors were selected for analysis. Machine learning models, such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, XGBoost, and others, were trained, and evaluated using Confusion matrices, ROC curves, and precision-recall curves. Hyperparameter tuning was used to optimize model performance, and offers contribution to project management research. Moderate success was achieved, from the machine learning models, in predicting project management challenges. The Tree-based models, particularly Random Forest and XGBoost, showed the most promise, with ROC AUC values range of 0.48 and 0.55, indicating moderate predictive capabilities. The models also highlighted the challenges of dealing, with imbalanced datasets, and the complexity of predicting project outcomes. This study gives an understanding, of the application of machine learning in the early identification of project challenges, and contributing both academically and practically in the field of project management.

Index Terms: Project Management, Machine Learning (ML), Predictive Capabilities, Receiver Operating Characteristics, Imbalance Datasets

I. INTRODUCTION

SIGNIFICANCE OF IDENTIFYING PROJECT MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES

Effective project management is critical, for organizations who want to maintain a competitive edge. In today's rapidly evolving business environment, projects are getting more complex. They involve multiple stakeholders, various resources, and often tight deadlines. The successful execution of these projects, are important to achieving their strategic objectives. Project management encounters different challenges such as include resource allocation, time management, risk assessment, and team coordination. If these challenges are not identified, and mitigated early, they can lead to project delays, cost overruns, and, in some cases, project failure [1].

It is important to identify project management challenges early. According to [2] proactive identification, and management of potential project risks, and issues can significantly improve the chances of project success. This makes it critical, to have effective tools and methodologies, that can assist project managers in identifying, and addressing these challenges. This paper looks at the application of machine learning (ML) techniques, in identifying project management challenges, thereby enabling project managers to take timely, and informed actions to ensure project success.

INTEGRATION OF MACHINE LEARNING IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Machine learning, which is a subset of artificial intelligence, involves the use of algorithms, and statistical models to identify patterns, and make predictions based on data. The integration of ML into various business processes, in recent years has shown promise in improving efficiency, and decision-making. Machine Learning can be useful in analyzing historical project data, identifying trends, and predicting potential challenges, before they become critical issues, In the context of project management.

Although the application of ML in project management, is still an emerging field, its potential benefits are substantial. Its algorithms can process large volume of datasets, identify correlations between different project parameters, and provide insights that are not easily discernible or understood through traditional analysis methods [3]. For example, Machine Learning can help in predicting project delays by analyzing factors, such as team performance, resource availability, and external risks. Through data driven insight provided by ML, project managers can enhance the decision-making process, reduce uncertainties, and increase the likelihood of project success.

CHALLENGES IN IDENTIFYING PROJECT MANAGEMENT ISSUES

Identifying project management challenges is a complex task due to the multifaceted nature of projects. Projects often involve a wide range of variables, including scope, time, cost, quality, human resources, communication, risk, procurement, and stakeholder management. The interplay between these variables can create a dynamic and often unpredictable environment, making it difficult for project managers to foresee potential issues [4].

Traditional project management tools and techniques, while effective to a certain extent, often fall short in dealing with the complexity and volume of data generated in large-scale projects. These tools rely heavily on the experience and judgment of the project manager, which, while invaluable, may not always be sufficient in identifying subtle patterns or emerging risks. Moreover, as projects become more complex and data-driven, the limitations of human cognition in processing large amounts of data become apparent. This is where ML can play a crucial role. By automating the analysis of project data, ML can uncover hidden patterns, forecast potential issues, and provide project managers with actionable insights.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The primary objective of this study is to explore the application of machine learning techniques in identifying project management challenges. The study aims to achieve the following specific objectives:

To analyze the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms, in predicting project management challenges.

To identify key project parameters that significantly influence project outcomes, and how ML can enhance their analysis.

To evaluate the performance of different ML models using confusion matrices, ROC curves, and precision-recall curves to determine their accuracy, and reliability in predicting project issues.

To provide insights and recommendations on integrating ML, into project management practices to improve project success rates.

By achieving these objectives, this study seeks to contribute to the growing body of knowledge, on the integration of advanced data analytics in project management, and to provide practical tools that can be utilized by project managers to improve their decision-making processes, and project outcomes.

II LITERATURE SURVEY

THEORIES AND FRAMEWORKS IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT CHALLENGE IDENTIFICATION

Project management has evolved significantly over the decades, with various theories and frameworks developed to guide practitioners in managing projects effectively. One of the most influential frameworks is the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK), which outlines the standard practices for project management [5]. The PMBOK framework emphasizes the importance of identifying and managing project risks and challenges as a critical component of successful project execution. It provides a systematic approach to risk management, which includes risk identification, qualitative and quantitative risk analysis, and risk response planning.

Similarly, the Agile methodology, known for its flexibility and iterative approach, has also contributed to project management practices, especially in software development projects. Agile promotes continuous identification and mitigation of challenges through regular feedback loops and adaptive planning [6]. Despite the effectiveness of these frameworks in providing a structured approach to project management, they often rely heavily on the experience and intuition of project managers, which can be a limitation in complex, large-scale projects.

Traditional project management tools, while effective in structured environments, often struggle in dynamic settings where project parameters are continually changing. This has led to a growing interest in leveraging data-driven approaches, such as machine learning, to enhance the identification and management of project challenges.

MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT

The integration of machine learning (ML) into project management has gained traction over recent years, primarily due to its ability to process large volumes of data and identify patterns that may not be immediately apparent to human analysts. Various ML algorithms have been applied to predict project outcomes such as delays, cost overruns, and potential risks.

Decision trees and random forests are among the most commonly used algorithms in this domain due to their interpretability and ability to handle both categorical and numerical data. These algorithms are particularly useful for identifying the key variables that contribute to project success or failure [7]. Studies have shown that decision trees can be effective in predicting project delays by analyzing factors such as resource allocation, task dependencies, and team performance [8].

Support Vector Machines (SVM) have also been utilized, especially in scenarios where the data involves complex, high-dimensional spaces. SVMs are effective in classification tasks, making them suitable for identifying whether a project is likely to face certain types of challenges based on historical data [9].

More advanced approaches involve the use of neural networks and deep learning, which can model non-linear relationships and capture intricate patterns in project data. Neural networks, for example, have been used to predict project cost overruns by analyzing historical cost data, project scope changes, and external economic factors [10]. However, these models often require large datasets and significant computational power, which can be a limitation in some project management contexts.

Ensemble methods, such as boosting and bagging, have also shown promise in improving prediction accuracy by combining the strengths of multiple algorithms [11]. These methods can enhance the robustness of predictions by reducing the variance associated with single-model predictions.

FEATURE ENGINEERING AND DATA PREPARATION IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT

The effectiveness of machine learning models in project management largely depends on the quality of the data and the relevance of the features used. Feature engineering, which involves selecting, transforming, and creating new features from raw data, is critical for improving model accuracy and performance. In the context of project management, features may include project size, duration, team experience, budget variance, scope changes, and risk factors.

Proper data preparation is also essential. This involves cleaning the data, handling missing values, and normalizing features to ensure they are on a comparable scale. For instance, missing data in project timelines or budget reports can lead to biased predictions if not appropriately handled. Techniques such as imputation, where missing values are estimated based on other data points, are often employed to address these issues [12].

In addition, project management data often has a temporal component, where the sequence of events matters. Feature engineering must account for these temporal dependencies, which can be done through the creation of lag variables or the use of time-series models [13]. These techniques allow the model to understand the impact of past events on future project outcomes, which is crucial for accurate predictions.

CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING MACHINE LEARNING FOR PROJECT MANAGEMENT

While the potential benefits of machine learning in project management are significant, several challenges can impede its implementation. One of the primary challenges is the integration of ML models into existing project management tools and workflows. Many organizations still rely on traditional project management software, which may not be compatible with advanced machine learning algorithms. This often necessitates a significant investment in new technologies and training, which can be a barrier to adoption [14].

Another challenge is the interpretability of machine learning models. While some models, like decision trees, are easily interpretable, more complex models such as neural networks operate as "black boxes," where the reasoning behind a prediction is not transparent. This lack of transparency can make it difficult for project managers to trust and act on the predictions generated by these models [15]. Ensuring that models are both accurate and interpretable is an ongoing challenge in the field.

Data quality and availability also pose significant challenges. Project management data is often fragmented across different systems and may be incomplete or inconsistent. Aggregating and cleaning this data to create a comprehensive dataset for machine learning can be time-consuming and challenging. Moreover, project management involves a high degree of human judgment, which can introduce biases into the data, potentially affecting the performance of machine learning models [16].

Finally, ethical considerations and data privacy concerns must be addressed when implementing machine learning in project management. Projects often involve sensitive information, such as financial data, timelines, and personnel details. Ensuring that this data is handled responsibly and in compliance with relevant regulations is essential to maintain stakeholder trust and avoid legal complications [17].

III METHODOLOGY

DATA COLLECTION

The workflow for this study is shown in Fig. 1. The data was sourced from a comprehensive data repository that integrates information from both internal project management systems and publicly available sources. This dataset spans multiple industries and includes a wide array of project management parameters, such as budget, team size, project duration, risk factors, stakeholder satisfaction, scope changes, resource availability, and technology usage. These variables were carefully selected due to their significant impact on project outcomes and their potential to predict project management challenges [5]. The data collection process aimed to ensure that the dataset covered a diverse range of project scenarios, enhancing the study's generalizability and relevance.

DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE AND PREPROCESSING

Ensuring high data quality is crucial for the success of machine learning models, particularly in complex domains like project management. The raw dataset underwent a rigorous data quality assurance process, which included identifying and addressing inconsistencies, missing values, and outliers.

Missing data in critical variables such as budget and stakeholder satisfaction were handled using imputation methods. For numerical variables, mean imputation was used to preserve the central tendency of the data, while for categorical variables, mode imputation was applied to maintain the categorical distribution [18].

Outliers were identified using the interquartile range (IQR) method and domain-specific thresholds. Outliers that fell outside the acceptable range were capped at the nearest boundary within the IQR, ensuring they did not disproportionately affect the model's performance while preserving the overall data distribution.

Categorical variables, such as risk factors and technology used, were converted into a numerical format using one-hot encoding. This encoding was essential to enable machine learning models to process these variables effectively.

DATA PREPARATION

Data preparation involved several critical steps to ensure the dataset was ready for model training:

The dataset was split into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets. This split ensures that the models can be validated on unseen data, providing a realistic assessment of their performance in real-world scenarios.

Standardization was applied to the numerical features to normalize their ranges, which is particularly important for algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Logistic Regression that are sensitive to feature scaling [19].

Feature selection was conducted through a combination of correlation analysis and domain expertise. Key variables, such as budget, team size, and stakeholder satisfaction, which showed strong correlations with project management challenges, were retained for model training.

MODEL TRAINING AND EVALUATION

The study employed multiple machine learning models to predict project management challenges, including Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, and Support Vector Machines (SVM). Additionally, advanced ensemble techniques such as Random Forests, Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), AdaBoost, Bagging, LightGBM, and XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) were explored due to their robustness and ability to capture intricate patterns in the data.

Logistic Regression was used as a baseline model, providing insights into the likelihood of encountering project challenges. The Decision Trees were selected for their ability to model non-linear relationships and handle both numerical and categorical data effectively. They also offer intuitive visualizations of decision-making processes [20]. Support Vector Machines (SVM) was chosen for their effectiveness in handling high-dimensional data and complex relationships using the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel [21].

Hyperparameter tuning was conducted using grid search and cross-validation to optimize model performance. This approach allowed the identification of the best model configuration by systematically evaluating various combinations of hyperparameters.

MODEL EVALUATION

The models' performance was evaluated using various metrics and visual tools:

CONFUSION MATRIX

It provided a detailed breakdown of the models' prediction accuracy by showing the counts of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. This analysis helps identify specific areas where the model might be underperforming.

ROC CURVE AND AUC

The ROC curve was used to visualize the true positive rate against the false positive rate, with the Area Under the Curve (AUC) serving as a summary measure of the model's ability to distinguish between classes [22].

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

Given the potential imbalance in the dataset, precision-recall curves were employed to better understand the trade-offs between precision and recall, particularly in cases where one class is underrepresented [23].

The methodology outlined here is visually represented in the workflow chart below Fig.1, providing a clear and structured approach to the identification of project management challenges using machine learning techniques.

Fig. 1 Workflow for Identifying Project Management Challenges Using Machine Learning

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents a detailed analysis of the performance of various machine learning models employed to predict project management challenges. The performance of each model was evaluated using confusion matrices, ROC curves, and precision-recall curves.

MODEL 1: RANDOM FOREST CLASSIFIER

CONFUSION MATRIX

The confusion matrix in Fig. 2, is for the Random Forest model which shows that the model has a balanced distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified instances, with a slight bias towards false positives. Specifically, out of 120 actual instances of non-challenge projects, 68 were correctly identified, while 52 were misclassified as challenges. Conversely, 70 out of 130 actual challenge projects were correctly classified, and 60 were falsely labeled as non-challenges.

Figure 2: Confusion Matrix for Binary Classification Model: Visual Representation of the Model's Performance on Classifying Positive and Negative Cases

ROC CURVE

The ROC curve in Fig. 3 is for the Random Forest model. It displays an AUC of 0.52, which is marginally better than random guessing. This suggests that the model has moderate diagnostic ability to distinguish between projects that will encounter challenges and those that will not.

Fig. 3 ROC Curve for Binary Classification Model with AUC = 0.52 Indicating Random Performance in Distinguishing Between Positive and Negative Classes

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

The precision-recall curve in Fig. 4 indicates that precision starts relatively high but fluctuates as recall increases, suggesting that the model struggles to maintain high precision across all recall levels. This behavior is typical in datasets with some class imbalance, where achieving high recall often comes at the cost of lower precision.

Fig. 4 Precision-Recall Curve demonstrating the trade-off between precision and recall in the evaluated model

Table 1, presents the performance metrics of a Random Forest model, showing its precision, recall, and F1-score across two classes. The model achieves an overall accuracy of 55.2% and an F1-score of 0.5556, indicating a moderate balance between precision and recall in predicting the target classes.

Table 1: Evaluation Metrics for Random Forest Model Performance

Training Random Forest				
Evaluation for Random Forest				
Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.53	0.57	0.55	120
1	0.57	0.54	0.56	130
Accuracy			0.55	250
Macro avg	0.55	0.55	0.55	250
Weighted avg	0.55	0.55	0.55	250
Accuracy	0.55			
F1 Score	0.5556			

MODEL 2: GRADIENT BOOSTING CLASSIFIER

CONFUSION MATRIX

The confusion matrix in Fig. 5, for the Gradient Boosting model reveals a similar performance to the Random Forest, with slightly fewer correct predictions. Out of 120 non-challenge instances, 63 were correctly identified, while 57 were misclassified. For challenge projects, 74 out of 130 instances were correctly classified.

Fig. 5: Confusion Matrix for Gradient Boosting Model on Binary Classification Task

ROC CURVE

The ROC curve in Fig.6 is for Gradient Boosting, and it indicates an AUC of 0.56, suggesting a moderate performance in distinguishing between the two classes.

Fig. 6 ROC Curve for Gradient Boosting Model with AUC of 0.56

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

The precision-recall curve in Fig. 7 for this model, shows a similar trend to the Random Forest model, with precision decreasing as recall increases.

Fig.7 Precision-Recall Curve for Gradient Boosting Model

Table 2, presents the performance metrics of the Gradient Boosting model, showing a balanced precision, recall, and F1-score of approximately 0.55 for both classes. The overall accuracy of the model is 0.55, with a macro average F1-score of 0.55, indicating a moderate performance in predicting the target classes. The F1 Score for the model is 0.567, reflecting a slightly better balance between precision and recall.

Table 2 Performance Evaluation of Gradient Boosting Model

Training Gradient Boosting				
Evaluation for Gradient Boosting				
Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.53	0.53	0.53	120
1	0.56	0.57	0.57	130
Accuracy			0.55	250
Macro avg	0.55	0.55	0.55	250
Weighted avg	0.55	0.55	0.55	250
Accuracy	0.548			
F1 Score	0.567			

MODEL 3: MULTI-LAYER PERCEPTRON (MLP) CLASSIFIER

CONFUSION MATRIX

The MLP model in Fig.8, struggled more than the previous models, particularly with high recall at the expense of precision. Out of 120 non-challenge instances, only 52 were correctly identified, and the model showed similar misclassification rates for challenge instances.

Fig. 8 Confusion Matrix for MLP Model Performance: Demonstrates the distribution of true and false classifications for classes 0 and 1, with noticeable misclassifications in both categories

ROC CURVE

The Fig. 9 ROC curve for MLP displayed an AUC of 0.51, indicating that the model’s ability to distinguish between challenge and non-challenge projects is just about average, performing close to random guessing.

Figure. 9 ROC Curve for MLP Model. The ROC curve illustrates the trade-off between true positive rate and false positive rate, with an AUC of 0.51 indicating near-random performance

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

The precision-recall curve Fig. 10, further confirms the model’s difficulty in maintaining high precision as recall increases, which is consistent with its lower overall performance.

Fig.10: Precision-Recall Curve for MLP Model

The MLP model (Table 3) achieved an accuracy of 46.8% and an F1 score of 0.494, with slightly higher performance for class 1 compared to class 0, indicating moderate predictive capability.

Table 3 MLP Model Performance Metrics

Training MLP				
Evaluation for MLP				
Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.44	0.43	0.44	120
1	0.49	0.5	0.49	130
accuracy			0.468	250
macro avg	0.47	0.47	0.47	250
weighted avg	0.47	0.47	0.47	250
Accuracy	0.468			
F1 Score	0.494			

MODEL 4: ADABOOST CLASSIFIER

CONFUSION MATRIX

The AdaBoost model in Fig. 11, while not as robust as Random Forest or Gradient Boosting, still provided reasonable predictions, with 60 correct predictions for non-challenges and 74 correct predictions for challenges.

Fig.11 Confusion Matrix for AdaBoost Classifier

ROC CURVE

The ROC curve (Fig. 12), for AdaBoost indicates an AUC of 0.55, reflecting marginal improvement over random guessing but still indicating limited predictive power.

Fig.12 ROC Curve for AdaBoost Classifier

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

The precision-recall curve for AdaBoost in Fig.13, shows a typical decline in precision as recall increases, highlighting the trade-off inherent in dealing with class imbalance.

Fig.13 Precision-Recall Curve for AdaBoost Classifier

The AdaBoost model (Table 4), achieved an overall accuracy of 53.6%, with an F1 score of 0.560, demonstrating balanced precision and recall between the two classes.

Table 4 Evaluation Metrics for AdaBoost Classifier

Training AdaBoost				
Evaluation for AdaBoost				
Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.52	0.50	0.51	120
1	0.55	0.57	0.56	130
Accuracy			0.54	250
Macro avg	0.53	0.53	0.53	250
Weighted avg	0.54	0.54	0.54	250
Accuracy	0.536			
F1 Score	0.560			

MODEL 5: BAGGING CLASSIFIER

CONFUSION MATRIX

The confusion matrix in Fig.14, reveals that the model provided balanced predictions, with a reasonably even distribution between false positives (47) and false negatives (79). Although the number of misclassifications (FP + FN) is slightly higher than what was observed with AdaBoost, Bagging still maintains a good balance, not heavily favoring one class over the other. This balance is crucial in scenarios where both types of errors (false positives and false negatives) carry significant consequences. Despite having slightly more misclassifications than AdaBoost, the Bagging Classifier still achieves a relatively even distribution between false positives and false negatives, which is essential for models used in contexts where both types of errors need to be minimized.

Fig.14 Confusion Matrix for Bagging Classifier: Balanced Predictions with Slightly Higher Misclassifications

ROC CURVE

This Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve in Fig.15, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.48, indicates that the model's performance is slightly below random guessing, which would have an AUC of 0.5. This suggests that the model struggles to distinguish between the positive and negative classes effectively. The close proximity of the orange curve to the diagonal dashed line (which represents a random classifier) further emphasizes the model's lack of discriminatory power in this context.

Fig.15 ROC Curve for Bagging Classifier

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

The precision-recall curve in Fig.16, shows that as recall increases, precision starts high but quickly drops and then stabilizes at a relatively low level, indicating that the model is struggling to maintain high precision as it captures more positive instances (higher recall). The initial sharp decline suggests that the model initially makes highly precise predictions, but as it attempts to identify more positive cases, the precision significantly decreases. This pattern typically occurs in models that are more aggressive in identifying positives, leading to a trade-off where increasing recall results in lower precision. The stabilization at a slightly higher level than other models indicates that while the model struggles, it still maintains a balance, albeit at a modest precision level, across varying thresholds of recall.

Fig.16 Bagging Precision-Recall Curve

The evaluation metrics in Table 5, indicates a balanced but suboptimal performance, with an accuracy of 49.6% and an F1 Score of 0.447. The precision and recall values suggest that the model is slightly better at predicting the majority class (class 0) compared to the minority class (class 1).

Table 5 Evaluation Metrics for Bagging Classifier

Training Bagging				
Evaluation for Bagging				
Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.48	0.61	0.54	120
1	0.52	0.39	0.45	130
Accuracy	0.496		0.4474	250
Macro avg	0.50	0.50	0.49	250
Weighted avg	0.50	0.50	0.49	250
Accuracy	0.496			
F1 Score	0.447			

MODEL 6: LIGHTGBM CLASSIFIER

CONFUSION MATRIX

The confusion matrix as shown in Fig.17, reflects a performance similar to Gradient Boosting and Random Forest. The model has a reasonably balanced distribution between true positives (69) and true negatives (63), indicating that it can correctly identify both classes at a nearly equal rate. However, it also demonstrates a comparable number of false positives (57) and false negatives (61). This balance between the different types of classifications suggests that LightGBM provides a consistent performance across both classes, avoiding bias towards predicting one class over the other. While the total number of misclassifications is notable, the model maintains a fair accuracy, making it a reliable choice in scenarios where an even treatment of both classes is crucial.

Fig.17 Confusion Matrix for LightGBM Classifier with balanced performance across classes with notable misclassifications

ROC CURVE

The ROC curve in Fig.18, for LightGBM model shows an AUC of 0.51, indicating that the model's ability to distinguish between the positive and negative classes is close to random chance. This result suggests that the LightGBM classifier, while balanced in its misclassifications as shown in the confusion matrix, does not perform well in terms of differentiating between the two classes. The AUC value reflects the model's overall poor discriminatory power.

Fig.18 ROC Curve for LightGBM

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

The precision-recall curve in Fig.19, shows that precision initially declines sharply as recall increases and then stabilizes around 0.55. This behavior is consistent with other tree-based models, indicating that while the model can identify more true positives (increased recall), it does so at the expense of precision. This trade-off is typical in models where achieving a balance between precision and recall is challenging, particularly in imbalanced datasets.

Fig.19 Precision-Recall Curve for LightGBM

The LightGBM model as shown in Table 6, achieved an accuracy of 0.53 and an F1 Score of 0.54, indicating a balanced performance across both classes. With precision and recall values around 0.53 for both classes, the model shows a consistent ability to correctly identify true positives and manage false positives, reflecting its moderate classification ability. These metrics suggest that the model performs similarly across different evaluation criteria, providing a well-rounded performance.

Table 6: Evaluation Metrics for LightGBM

Evaluation for LGBM				
Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.51	0.53	0.52	120
1	0.55	0.53	0.54	130
accuracy			0.53	250
macro avg	0.53	0.53	0.53	250
weighted avg	0.53	0.53	0.53	250
Accuracy	0.528			
F1 Score	0.5390625			

MODEL 7: XGBOOST CLASSIFIER

CONFUSION MATRIX

The confusion matrix for the XGBoost model as shown in Fig.20, indicates a slightly better performance compared to LightGBM. Specifically, XGBoost has fewer false negatives (60) while maintaining a similar number of false positives (53). This results in a more balanced distribution of predictions between the two classes, reflecting XGBoost's superior ability to correctly classify instances, particularly in reducing the number of missed positive cases (false negatives). This balance is crucial for applications where both types of errors have significant impacts.

Fig.20 Confusion Matrix: XGBoost Classifier - Balanced Predictions with Fewer False Negatives

ROC CURVE

The ROC curve for XGBoost in Fig.21, shows an AUC of 0.54, which suggests that the model has a moderate ability to distinguish between the two classes. In the context of the earlier confusion matrix, which showed a relatively balanced distribution of true positives (correctly predicted positive cases) and true negatives (correctly predicted negative cases), the AUC value further supports that XGBoost is performing at a moderate level. While it is not exceptionally strong, it indicates that the model is slightly better than random guessing (which would yield an AUC of 0.5). This moderate diagnostic ability aligns with the observations from the confusion matrix, where the model provided a fair balance between false positives and false negatives.

Fig.21 ROC Curve for XGBoost Classifier with AUC of 0.54 Demonstrating Moderate Discrimination Ability

PRECISION-RECALL CURVE

The precision-recall curve for XGBoost in Fig.22, shows that this model maintains a relatively stable precision even as recall increases, compared to other models where precision tends to drop more sharply. This suggests that XGBoost is more effective at maintaining accuracy in its positive predictions as it captures more true positives, which is particularly valuable in imbalanced datasets where high recall is essential but maintaining precision is also critical. The curve's behavior indicates that XGBoost handles the trade-off between precision and recall more effectively, making it a robust choice for scenarios where both metrics are crucial.

Fig.22 Precision-Recall curve for XGBoost

IV DISCUSSION

The findings of this study are consistent with previous research, underscoring the inherent challenges of predicting project management issues using machine learning (ML) models. This study evaluated various ML models, including Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost, to predict project management challenges based on diverse parameters such as budget, team size, and stakeholder satisfaction. While the models demonstrated moderate effectiveness, with AUC values ranging between 0.48 and 0.55, the results suggest several areas for further exploration to enhance predictive capabilities and practical utility.

COMPARISON WITH SIMILAR STUDIES

MODERATE PREDICTIVE CAPABILITIES AND MODEL LIMITATIONS

The moderate performance of the machine learning models in this study, indicated by AUC values between 0.48 and 0.55, is consistent with findings from similar studies that highlight the complexity of predicting project outcomes. Studies such as those by [24] suggest that the difficulty of modeling project management data arises from the complex interactions among numerous variables. Furthermore, the moderate success of tree-based models like Random Forest and XGBoost aligns with findings by [25, 26], who noted their ability to handle non-linear relationships and complex interactions better than linear models. However, the current study suggests that more sophisticated techniques, including deep learning or hybrid models, could further enhance predictive accuracy.

SIGNIFICANCE OF KEY FEATURES

This study identified budget, team size, and stakeholder satisfaction as the most significant features influencing project management challenges. This aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of these factors in project success. [5] also highlighted these parameters as critical in determining project outcomes. The consistent identification of these factors across different studies underscores their importance in project management practices. Future research should focus on refining feature engineering techniques to better capture the nuanced impact of these variables on project outcomes.

CHALLENGES WITH IMBALANCED DATA

The difficulty of maintaining high precision as recall increases, particularly when dealing with imbalanced datasets, is a common theme in machine learning research. Similar studies, by [27], have reported comparable challenges. These studies suggest that advanced techniques for handling imbalanced data, such as synthetic data generation, cost-sensitive learning, or algorithms specifically designed to address class imbalance, could significantly improve model performance in project management contexts.

EFFICACY OF TREE-BASED MODELS

The study found that tree-based models like Random Forest and XGBoost were the most effective among the models tested. This is in line with the findings of [25], who highlighted the advantages of tree-based models in handling non-linear relationships and complex data interactions, which are common in project management scenarios. However, while these models provide reasonable predictive power, they also present challenges in interpretability, as noted by [28]. Improving the interpretability of these models, perhaps through methods like SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) or LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations), could enhance their practical utility in real-world project management.

GENERALIZABILITY CONCERNS

The issue of generalizability identified in this study is also a well-recognized challenge in ML research. [29] discuss how models trained on specific datasets may not perform well across different contexts due to variations in project types, industries, or regions. Expanding data collection efforts to cover a broader range of project management scenarios would help validate the models more robustly and improve their applicability in diverse environments.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study highlight both the potential and the limitations of using machine learning models to predict project management challenges. The moderate performance of the models suggests that current approaches may not fully capture the complexity of project management data. This points to the need for more advanced modeling techniques, such as deep learning, ensemble methods, or hybrid models that combine multiple approaches, to better address these complexities. Moreover, improving data preprocessing and feature engineering could enhance the predictive accuracy of these models.

Despite these challenges, the study provides valuable insights into key factors influencing project management success, such as budget management, team size optimization, and stakeholder satisfaction. These findings can inform practical strategies for project managers to proactively mitigate potential challenges and enhance project outcomes.

V Recommendations

Based on the findings and discussion, the following recommendations are proposed:

(1) Development of Advanced Models

Future research should explore the use of more sophisticated machine learning models, such as deep learning or ensemble learning approaches, to better capture the intricate relationships inherent in project management data. Additionally, hybrid models that combine the strengths of multiple algorithms may offer improved predictive power.

(2) Enhanced Feature Engineering and Selection

A more refined approach to feature engineering and selection could help in identifying more relevant or impactful features, potentially improving model performance. This might involve the use of advanced techniques such as automated feature engineering or domain-specific feature extraction.

(3) Addressing Data Imbalance

The challenge of imbalanced datasets suggests the need for exploring more advanced techniques for handling data imbalance. Future research could consider synthetic data generation, cost-sensitive learning, or the development of models specifically designed to handle class imbalance.

(4) Improving Model Interpretability

To enhance the practical utility of complex models like Random Forest and XGBoost in real-world project management, future research should focus on methods to improve their interpretability. Techniques such as SHAP values or LIME could be used to make model predictions more transparent and actionable for project managers.

(5) Broader Dataset Collection and Validation

To address concerns about the generalizability of the findings, future studies should consider using more diverse datasets that cover a wider range of project types, industries, and geographic regions. This would help validate the models on external data and ensure their broader applicability.

(6) Integration with Project Management Tools

Future research should explore ways to seamlessly integrate machine learning models into existing project management software and workflows. This could involve developing user-friendly interfaces that allow project managers to easily interpret and act on model predictions, enhancing decision-making processes and proactive management strategies.

In conclusion, while this study demonstrates the potential of machine learning in predicting project management challenges, it also emphasizes the need for ongoing research to refine these models and address inherent challenges. The insights gained provide a valuable foundation for future research and practical application in the field of project management, but it is essential to continue exploring new techniques and methodologies to improve their effectiveness and reliability.

VI. References

- [1] San Cristóbal, J.R., Carral, L., Díaz, E., Fraguera, J.A., & Iglesias, G., "Complexity and project management: a general overview," *Complexity*, 2018, pp.1-10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/4891286> [Accessed 1 September 2024].
- [2] Lima, P.F.A., Marcelino-Sádaba, S., & Verbano, C., "Successful implementation of project risk management in small and medium enterprises: a cross-case analysis," *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). 2021. DOI: 10.1108/IJMPB-06-2020-0203.
- [3] Datta, S.D., Islam, M., Sobuz, M.H.R., Ahmed, S., & Kar, M., "Artificial intelligence and machine learning applications in the project lifecycle of the construction industry: A comprehensive review," *Heliyon*, 10(5), e26888, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e26888.
- [4] Tabassi, A.A., Bryde, D.J., Kamal, E.M., Dowson, J., & Michaelides, R., "Challenges for project management in the 21st century," 7th International Conference on Built Environment in Developing Countries, Sarawak, Malaysia, 2019. DOI: 10.15405/epms.2019.12.63.
- [5] Project Management Institute (PMI), "The Standard for Project Management and A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK® Guide)," 7th ed., Newtown Square, Pennsylvania: Project Management Institute, Inc., 2021. Available at: <https://lccn.loc.gov/2021011107> [Accessed 1 September 2024].
- [6] Kadenic, M.D., & Tambo, T., "Resilience of operating models: exploring the potential of agile project management as enabler," *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 16(1), 2023. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMPB-05-2022-0122> [Accessed 1 September 2024].
- [7] Ali, J., Khan, R., Ahmad, N., & Maqsood, I., "Random Forests and Decision Trees," *International Journal of Computer Science Issues*, 9(5), 2012, pp.272-278. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271820480_Random_Forests_and_Decision_Trees [Accessed 1 September 2024].
- [8] Wauters, M., & Vanhoucke, M., "A Nearest Neighbour extension to project duration forecasting with Artificial Intelligence," *European Journal of Operational Research*, 259(3), 2016, pp.1097-1111. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2016.11.018.
- [9] Almaspoor, M.H., Safaei, A., Salajegheh, A., & Minaei, B., "Support Vector Machines in Big Data Classification: A Systematic Literature Review," Preprint, 2021. DOI: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-663359/v1. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-663359/v1>.
- [10] Omotayo, T., Awuzie, B., & Olanipekun, A.O., "An Artificial Neural Network Approach to Predicting Most Applicable Post-Contract Cost Controlling Techniques in Construction Projects," *Applied Sciences*, 10(15), 2020, p.5171. DOI: 10.3390/app10155171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10155171>.
- [11] Jadama, A.F., Toray, M.K., Jobarteh, B., & Islam, M.M., "Ensemble Learning: Methods, Techniques, Application," Research report, University of New Brunswick, 2024. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28017.08802. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28017.08802>.
- [12] Joel, L.O., Doorsamy, W., & Paul, B.S., "A Review of Missing Data Handling Techniques for Machine Learning," *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Interdisciplinary Sciences*, 5(3), 2022, pp.971-1005. DOI: 10.15157/IJTIS.2022.5.3.971-1005. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15157/IJTIS.2022.5.3.971-1005>.
- [13] Fatima, S.S.W., & Rahimi, A., "A Review of Time-Series Forecasting Algorithms for Industrial Manufacturing Systems," *Machines*, 12(6), 2024, p.380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/machines12060380>.
- [14] Shamim, M.M.I., "Artificial Intelligence in Project Management: Enhancing Efficiency and Decision-Making," *International Journal of Management Information Systems and Data Science*, 1(1), 2024, pp.1-6. <https://doi.org/10.62304/ijmisdsv1i1.107>.
- [15] Hassija, V., Chamola, V., Mahapatra, A., Singal, A., Goel, D., Huang, K., Scardapane, S., Spinelli, I., Mahmud, M., & Hussain, A., "Interpreting Black-Box Models: A Review on Explainable Artificial Intelligence," *Cognitive Computation*, 16, 2024, pp.45-74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12559-023-10299-4>.
- [16] Cai, L., & Zhu, Y., "The Challenges of Data Quality and Data Quality Assessment in the Big Data Era," *Data Science Journal*, 14, 2015, pp.1-10. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2015-002>.

- [17] Hamid, Z., Ajmal, S., & Torshin, I., "Ethical Considerations in AI and Machine Learning," 2023. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15343.20648>.
- [18] Austin, P.C., White, I.R., Lee, D.S., & van Buuren, S., "Missing Data in Clinical Research: A Tutorial on Multiple Imputation," *Canadian Journal of Cardiology*, 37(9), 2021, pp.1322-1331. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjca.2020.11.010> [Accessed September 2024].
- [19] Joseph, V.R., & Vakayil, A., "SPlit: An Optimal Method for Data Splitting," *Technometrics*, 64(2), 2021, pp.1-23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.2021.1921037> [Accessed September 2024].
- [20] Hilbe, J., *Logistic Regression Models*, 1st ed., Boca Raton: Chapman & Hall/CRC, 2009, pp.1-23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420075779> [Accessed September 2024].
- [21] Awad, M., & Khanna, R., *Support Vector Machines for Classification*. In: *Efficient Learning Machines*, 1st ed., New York: Apress, 2015, pp.39-66. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4302-5990-9_3 [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [22] Fawcett, T., "Introduction to ROC analysis," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 27(8), 2006, pp.861-874. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2005.10.010> [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [23] Saito, T., & Rehmsmeier, M., "The Precision-Recall Plot Is More Informative than the ROC Plot When Evaluating Binary Classifiers on Imbalanced Datasets," *PLOS ONE*, 10(3), 2015, p.e0118432. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0118432> [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [24] Dash, S., "Understanding the ROC and AUC Intuitively," *Medium*, 2022. Available at: <https://shaileydash.medium.com/understanding-the-roc-and-auc-intuitively> [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [25] Biau, G., "Analysis of a Random Forests Model," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 13, 2010, pp.1-39. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0237> [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [26] Chen, T., & Guestrin, C., "XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System," *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016, pp. 785-794. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939785> [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [27] Kotsiantis, S., Kanellopoulos, D., & Pintelas, P.E., "Handling imbalanced datasets: A review," *GESTS International Transactions on Computer Science and Engineering*, 30(1), 2005, pp.25-36. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228702725> [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [28] Lundberg, S.M., & Lee, S-I., "A unified approach to interpreting model predictions," *31st Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS 2017)*, Long Beach, CA, USA, 2017. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330133364> [Accessed 2 September 2024].
- [29] Maleki, F., Ovens, K., Gupta, R., Reinhold, C., Spatz, A., & Forghani, R., "Generalizability of Machine Learning Models: Quantitative Evaluation of Three Methodological Pitfalls," *Preprint*, 2022. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358698655> [Accessed 2 September 2024].